

RUDYARD KIPLING AND HIS FAMOUS NOVEL "THE JUNGLE BOOK"**Jalolova Lobarkhon Sunnatullo kizi****Student of Navoi state pedagogical institute****jalolovalobarxon@gmail.com****+998913376473****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8133602>****ANNOTATION**

Following the declaration of independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan was forced to adopt new laws and resolutions to reflect the country's changing circumstances. To accomplish this task, new laws and resolutions were passed. The president of our nation paid attention to language acquisition.

The initiatives will contribute to the implementation of Presidential Decree Number 1875 from December 2012, which aims to improve foreign language teaching and learning in order to improve future Uzbekistan specialists' ability to communicate internationally and in all fields.

"The Law of learning foreign languages" and "The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the National Program of Personnel Training System" were both adopted for the first time in our nation's history. Language learning and teaching are currently given a lot of importance.

INTRODUCTION

When learning a new language, literature is the subject that students who want to master a language quickly and perfectly must learn thoroughly. Because they will be able to learn some statistics about the uniqueness of the target language through this. As a result, we learn the English language, which calls for the knowledge of English-language literature, especially that of the United States and the United Kingdom.

The life and identity of Joseph Rudyard Kipling

Joseph Rudyard Kipling (December 30, 1865, Bombay — January 18, 1936, London), was an English writer, poet and short story writer. The rich language of Kipling's works, full of metaphors, made a great contribution to the treasury of the English language. Rudyard Kipling was born in Bombay, in the family of John Lockwood Kipling, a professor at the local School of Art, and Alice (MacDonald) Kipling. He was named Rudyard, it is believed, in honor of the English Rudyard Lake, where his parents met. The early years, full of exotic sights and sounds of India, were very happy for the future writer. But at the age of 5, together with his sister, he goes to study in England. For 6 years he lived in a private boarding house, the owner of which (Madame Rosa) mistreated him, punished him. This attitude affected him so much that he suffered from insomnia for the rest of his life. At the age of 12, his parents arrange for him to attend a private Devon school so that he could then enroll in a prestigious military academy. The principal of the school was Cornell Price¹, a friend of Rudyard's father. It was he who began to encourage the boy's love of literature. Myopia did not allow Kipling to choose a military career, and the school did not give diplomas for admission to other universities. Impressed by the stories written at the college, his father finds him a job as a journalist in the editorial office of the Civil and Military Gazette, published in Lahore. In October 1882, Kipling returned to India and began working as a journalist. In his spare time, he writes short stories

¹ Brian Gardner, *The Public Schools: an historical survey* (Hamilton, 1973), p. 188

and poems, which are then published by the newspaper along with reports. The work of a reporter helps him to better understand the various aspects of the colonial life of the country. The first sales of his works began in 1883. The era of travel In the mid-80s, Kipling began to travel around Asia and the United States as a correspondent for the Allahabad newspaper Pioneer, with which he signed a contract to write travel essays. The popularity of his works is rapidly increasing, in 1888 and 1889 6 books with his stories were published, which brought him recognition. In 1889, he made a long trip to England, then visited Burma, China, Japan. He travels all over the USA, crosses the Atlantic Ocean and settles in London. He is beginning to be called the literary heir of Charles Dickens. In 1890, his first short story "The Light Went Out" (The Light That Failed) was published. The most famous poems of that time are "The Ballad of East and West" (The Ballad of East and West), as well as "The Last Song of Honest Thomas" (The Last Rhime of True Thomas). Career as a writer In London, he meets a young American publisher, Walcott Belystir, they are working together on the novel "Naulahka" (The Naulahka). In 1892, Belystir died of typhus, and soon after that Kipling married his sister Caroline. During the honeymoon, the bank in which Kipling had savings went bankrupt. The couple had only enough money left to get to Vermont (USA), where the Belystyr relatives lived. They have been living here for the next four years. At this time, the writer again begins to write for children; in 1894-95, the famous "The Jungle Book" (The Jungle Book) and "The Second Jungle Book" (The Second Jungle Book) were published.

The poetry collections "The Seven Seas" and "The white thesis" have also been published. Two children are being born soon: Josephine and Elsie. After a quarrel with his brother-in-law, Kipling and his wife returned to England in 1896. In 1897, the novel "Brave Navigators" (Captains Courageous) was published. In 1899, during a visit to the United States, his eldest daughter Josephine died of pneumonia, which was a huge blow for the writer. In 1899, he spent several months in South Africa, where he met Cecil Rhodes, a symbol of British imperialism. In 1901, the novel "Kim" (Kim), which is considered one of the best novels of the writer, was published. In Africa, he begins to select material for a new children's book, which was published in 1902 under the title "Fairy Tales just like that" (Just So Stories). In the same year, he buys a country house in Sussex County (England), where he remains until the end of his life. Here he writes his famous books "Puck from the Hills" (Puck of Pook's Hill) and "Rewards and Fairies" (Rewards and Fairies) — fairy tales of Old England, united by the narrator — elf Puck, taken from Shakespeare's plays. Simultaneously with literary activity, Kipling begins active political activity. He writes about the impending war with Germany, speaks in support of conservatives and against feminism. During the First World War, literary activity is becoming less saturated. Another blow for the writer was the death of his eldest son John in the First World War in 1915. Kipling and his wife worked in the Red Cross during the war. After the war, he became a member of the War Graves Commission. It was he who chose the biblical phrase "Their names will live forever" on the obelisks of memory. During one trip to France in 1922, he met the English King George V², with whom he then struck up a great friendship. The last days of the writer Kipling continued his literary activity until the early 30s, although success accompanied him less and less. Since 1915, the writer suffered from gastritis, which later turned out to be an ulcer. Rudyard Kipling died of a traumatic brain

² Clay, p. 39; Sinclair, pp. 46–47

hemorrhage on January 18, 1936 in London, only 3 days before George V. He is buried in Poets' Corner in Westminster Abbey.

THE THEME OF THE WORK IS THE JUNGLE BOOK.

The book consists of two parts. Some of the stories tell about Mowgli, about his life in the jungle among wild animals. At the age of two, the little son of a woodcutter gets lost in the jungle. The lame tiger Sher Khan is on his heels and wants to make him his prey. The child crawls to the lair of wolves. Father and Mother wolves accept him into their family and protect him from Sher Khan. They call him Mowgli, which means "frog" in translation. At the wolf pack council, Baloo the bear, who teaches the cubs the law of the jungle, and Bagheera the black panther, who pays the pack not to give the baby to Shere Khan, ask to let Mowgli live among the wolves.

Mowgli's intelligence and courage allow him to survive and get stronger in the difficult conditions of life in the jungle. His friends and patrons are Baloo bear, Bagheera, boa constrictor Kaa, the leader of the wolf pack Akelo. There are many adventures in his life, he learns to speak the language of all the inhabitants of the jungle, and this saves his life more than once. One day the monkeys take the boy to the Cold Lairs, a ruined Hindu city founded in the jungle several centuries ago. Bagheera, Baloo and Kaa come to the boy's aid and save him from the monkeys, who play with him like a toy.

Ten years after Mowgli's arrival in the jungle, the pack leader Akelo becomes old and can no longer patronize his pet. Many wolves hate Mowgli because they cannot stand his gaze and feel his inexplicable superiority. Shere Khan is waiting for the right moment to deal with Mowgli. Then, on Bagheera's advice, Mowgli brings fire from the village. On the Rock of the Council of the Wolf Pack, he demonstrates his strength to the animals, scorches the skin of Sher Khan, defends Akelo.

After that, he leaves the jungle and goes to the village, to the people. There, a woman named Messua takes him for her son, once dragged away by Shere Khan, and gives him shelter in her house. Mowgli learns the human language, gets used to the way of life of people, and then for a few months becomes a shepherd of a village herd of buffaloes. One day he learns from the wolves loyal to him that Shere Khan, who went to another part of the jungle to heal his wounds, has returned. Then Mowgli lures the tiger into a trap and directs a buffalo herd at him from two sides. Sher Khan is dying. A village hunter who has found out about the death of a tiger wants to get a hundred rupees for the capture of Sher Khan himself and wants to take his skin to the village. Mowgli won't let him do it. Then the hunter calls him a werewolf, and Messua and her husband are sorcerers. Mowgli with a tiger skin hides in the jungle. His named parents are going to be burned. Mowgli returns, helps them escape and get to the settlement of the British, from whom they can ask for protection. Mowgli sends wild elephants, buffaloes, and deer to the village, and they trample fields, destroy houses, disperse herds, so that residents are forced to seek shelter in some other place.

After the death of Shere Khan and the destruction of the village, Mowgli returns to the jungle, and now he lives especially well. He grows up to be a handsome, strong and intelligent young man. When he reaches the age of seventeen, the habitat of wolves is attacked by wild red dogs- dales. Each of them is weaker than a wolf, but they attack in hordes, they are hungry and kill all living things in their path. Mowgli, along with Kaa, lures them into a trap. The trick helps him to deal with most of the uninvited guests. Spring is coming, and Mowgli is drawn to

people. He says goodbye to his friends and finally goes to where Messua and her recently born child now live. Mowgli meets a girl, marries her and leads a normal way of life for a human being, but forever retains in his memory his first years spent in the jungle and the images of faithful friends.

Mowgli is a character with whom Kipling's two—volume book is strongly associated. The story of M. is given three stories in the first book and five in the second. The name of the hero was invented by the author and translated by him as "the frog". M. is the son of a woodcutter who got lost in the jungle at the age of two. The first encounter with wildlife almost turned into a disaster: M. could become a victim of the lame tiger Sher Khan, who considers the "human cub" his prey. The child is saved by the Father and Mother wolves, taking him into their family. At the council of the wolf pack in defense of M. the bear Baloo, who teaches the cubs the law of the jungle, and the black panther Bagheera, who buys the life of M. Thanks to his courage and intelligence, the boy becomes an equal member of the pack. He is helped by friends and patrons — Baloo, Bagheera, the wolf leader Akelo, python Kaa. M. develops rapidly, matures and matures. He learns the language of all the inhabitants of the jungle, and this saves his life more than once. At the same time, M. acquires more and more human traits. Some wolves instinctively hate M., because they can't stand his gaze. Shere Khan is only waiting for the right moment to deal with him. The aging Akelo is no longer able to resist the pack, and then M., on Bagheera's advice, brings fire from the village. From now on, all animals are forced to recognize the power of man. Having singed the skin of Sher Khan and protected Akelo, M. goes to the village, to the people. He is given shelter by a woman named Messua, from whom Sher Khan once stole his son. M. learns the human language and joins a new way of life. However, in the world of people, he had to face cruelty and injustice. M. lured Sher Khan into a trap by directing a buffalo herd at the tiger from both sides. One of the village hunters wants to get a hundred rupees for a tiger skin and calls M. a werewolf. The young man hides in the jungle, but then returns, because the villagers are going to burn Messua and her husband, accused of witchcraft. M. saves his foster parents, and sends a herd of wild elephants, buffaloes and deer to the village — they trample fields, destroy houses, disperse pets. People are forced to leave these places forever and look for another haven. M. again retreats into the jungle, where all the animals recognize his rights as a master and ruler. At the age of seventeen, M. he feels that he is irresistibly drawn to his own. He says goodbye to his friends and finally goes to where Messua lives with a recently born child. Having met a girl, M. marries her and begins to lead a normal way of life for a person, but the memories of the years spent in the jungle remain forever in his memory.

M. is one of the most beloved characters in children's literature. However, Kipling's book is largely addressed to adults, because it is about the place of man in nature. M.'s story, devoid of any scientific evidence, nevertheless became the strongest argument in defense of the Darwinian view of nature.

Rikki-Tikki-Tavi is a brave little mongoose, a fearless snake fighter. An English family nurses a barely alive mongoose and leaves him to live in his house. There are two cobras in the garden — Naga and Nagena. Snakes, wanting to drive R.T.T. away, plot to kill all people — husband and wife and their little son. The mongoose saves his patrons from certain death: he kills the formidable Naga, already hiding in the bathroom, then destroys the eggs, from which new

snakes were about to hatch, and finally rushes in pursuit of Nagena into her hole, where he deals with the vengeful cobra.

Critical analysis and reviews of the "Jungle Book"

"The Jungle Books" have enough encrypted imagery to be perceived outside of Kipling's public program. From that, the literary reading of them is especially contradictory. Harmless animalistic fantasy; expression of a new moral code of "activity" and "freedom"; preaching of brute force and aggressiveness; a hymn to the human in a man who triumphs over a beast — disputing judgments with each other. The assessments of Kipling's innovation are equally contradictory: imitation of artistic novelty at the expense of newspaper journalism; the external democratization of the dictionary, the ways of narration of the characters and the narrator; real, genuine talent (a well-known opinion of Hemingway). Therefore, such an examination of his works is still relevant when the individual characteristics of talent, the artist's social position, the concept of the world and genre-style innovation come into connection.

The methodology of the study of the work is determined by the following theoretical concepts: genre interaction is not a simple, even if quantitatively rich, addition of genres; stylistic novelty is not a combination, even with reservations ("organic fusion"), of various stylistic trends; both can be a system, and even more innovative, only if, if it is connected with the process of "germination" of some innovative individual grain. Fundamental works of scientists allow us to come to such an understanding of the genre and style.

Literary historians, developing the traditions of Russian democratic criticism in assessing Kipling (Kuprin), analyze mainly the contradictions of his work and ideology; it also concerns his "children's" works. The English-speaking Kiplingian is more multidimensional and specialized, but its common feature and disadvantage, arising from the methodology, is the separate discussion of artistic skill and ideology

In the course of the study, the term "genre synthesis" in relation to the "Jungle Books" was removed as inevitably suggesting the idea of combining (albeit "creative", "melting together", etc.) ready-made genre forms, the idea of a novel in short stories or cycles of short stories, than these books in no way they are not. It would be more accurate to characterize them as an experiment in the field of meaning and form; an experiment in the genre of the then young animalistic novel allows us to develop a special stylistic language for this genre with the help of various forms of fairy tale, reportage, journalism, lyrics, etc. In the age of the formation of sociology as a science and the spread of Darwinism not only as a biological theory, Kipling forced this genre to serve the purposes of artistic sociological research. Hence the "references to sources", both fabulous and imitating documentary: the story of a white seal with the Russian name Kotik "was told to me by a polar finch named Limmershin"; the story of the Eskimo Kotuko is carved on a Walrus bone (all the owners of the plate, steamships, and ports where she visited are indicated), "I found her among all junk in one house in Colombo and transferred it all, from edge to edge."

CONCLUSION

There is ample evidence to support theories that Rudyard Kipling's The Jungle Book helps determine the time when the British colonized India and the presence of orientalism in the novel itself. The novel supports two different and (both correct views) of who and what is Oriental or other, depending on what we are looking at. In addition, it has been proven that

the power and superiority given to Western nations contribute to the ability to colonize a nation by imposing their beliefs, ways and society on others to help "improve" these societies. The meaning of Kipling's sermon here is very clear: in order to justify the action, it is necessary to believe in the collective mission of the British, to believe that the "England of Dreams" is more important and more real than the empirical reality itself — "putty, copper, paint". Therefore, the well-known paradoxalist G. K. Chesterton was not so far from the truth when he reproached Kipling for the lack of true patriotism and claimed that he basically did not care which empire or country to use as a model. The British Empire exists in his mind only as an intelligible idea, as a myth, which, in the words of an English researcher, "gives moral content to everyday behavior, linking it with the transpersonal, collective task of the apocalyptic reconstruction of the world."

But, creating the imperial myth, Kipling is forced to constantly correlate it with the real reality from which he was born — he is forced to notice glaring inconsistencies between the desired and the actual, between the abstract drawing of a reasonable world order and its unattractive political embodiment. The fear that the Empire will not fulfill its mission forces him not only to preach, but also to denounce, demanding that the "Empire builders" comply with the highest moral law. His political poems and hymns of the nineties ("The Song of the Dead", "The Last Hymn", "The Anthem before the Battle", etc.) are polemically pointed against the boastful jingoism that has become widespread in many strata of English society: in them he urges the country not to revel in easy victories, but to soberly look into its own weaknesses and understand its purpose as selfless sacrifice, as selfless service to a "great goal". In Kipling's formulation, "the burden of the whites" is the subjugation of the lower races for their own good, not robbery and violence, but creative work and purity of thoughts, not arrogant complacency, but humility and patience.

Kipling's world is the world of the gap, the world on the threshold of future changes, the true meaning of which, so well known to us, is still hidden from the writer's gaze. Therefore, for example, Kipling's work was able to prepare revolutionary transformations of English—language verse among post—symbolists, influenced the development of the novel genre in Conrad, Sherwood Anderson, Hemingway, but - on the other hand - served as a prototype of "mass literature" and to a greater extent determined its genre repertoire. However, Kipling himself was hardly to blame for the emergence of those inhumane, destructive tendencies for culture that he had to anticipate and anticipate. Being mistaken, clinging to false ideals and values, he nevertheless always sought to sincerely serve the "common man", sought to help him overcome suffering and fear, teach him courage, perseverance and dedication to his chosen cause. In the words of one of his program poems, he was among those artists who ...

use the World assigned,

To hearten and make whole,

Not less than Gods have served mankind

Though vultures rend their souls.

Yes, Kipling's soul was tormented by kites, but he wrote not about this, but about how to live in spite of torments, and maybe this is the main clue to his relentless app.

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